

Molecular typing of the enteroaggregative *E.coli* heat-stable enterotoxin 1 gene (EAST1) in *E. coli* strains isolated from human and calves with diarrhea.

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Abstract

A total of 76 *E.coli* strains isolated from human and calves with diarrhea were tested for the presence of the Enteroaggregative *E.coli* heat-stable enterotoxin 1 gene (EAST1) by using PCR then gene has been sequenced, followed by PCR detection of different virulence factors genes including shiga toxins 1 and 2, intimin, aggR, hemolysin, heat labile toxin, heat stable toxin, F5 and F5 genes. The EAST1 gene was found in most human strains accompanied with LT and ST gene in Enterotoxigenic strains (O6:H16), aggR (Fimbrial antigen-specific gene) in Enteroaggregative strains (O126:H27) and with shiga toxins and intimin genes in Enterohemorrhagic strains (O157:H7 and O26:H11). Only 4 bovine strains (3 Enterotoxigenic strains and 1 enteropathogenic strain) with adherence factor F5 (K99) were also positive for the EAST1 gene. We concluded that the presence of EAST1 gene not restricted to Enteroaggregative *E.coli* but also present in other pathotypes in combination with certain virulence marker.

Key words: *E. coli*, Molecular typing, calves, diarrhea

Introduction

E. coli is an important member of the normal intestinal microflora of humans and other mammals. Usually *E. coli* and its host coexist in good health and with mutual benefit for decades. These commensal *E. coli* strains rarely cause disease where the normal gastrointestinal barriers are breached (Kaper, 2004)

Diarrhea remains one of the main sources of morbidity and mortality in today's world and a large proportion is caused by diarrheagenic *E. coli* in human and animals (Usein et al., 2009). The family of diarrheagenic *E. coli* encompass various members including enterohemorrhagic *E. coli* (EHEC), enteropathogenic *E. coli* (EPEC), enteroinvasive *E. coli* (EIEC), enterotoxigenic *E. coli* (ETEC), and more recently, diffusely adherent *E. coli* (DAEC) and enteroaggregative *E. coli* (EAEC) . These *E. coli* are classified in different pathotypes based

on the presence of specific virulence factors (Kaper, 2004). EAST1 (EnteroAggregative heat-Stable Toxin1) is encoded by the *astA* gene, a 117 bp long DNA sequence. EAST1 is thought to play a role in EAEC pathogenicity even if not all EAEC strains harbor the *astA* gene (Hunag et al., 1994). Epidemiological studies have associated this gene with *E. coli* pathotypes other than EAEC like ETEC and EHEC (Savarino et al., 1996).

Our study was conducted to investigate the prevalence of EAST1-gene in different pathotypes of *E. coli* isolated from diarrheal cases in both human and calves by using PCR and gene sequencing and its relation with other virulence markers.

Materials and methods

1-Sampling:

A total of 106 fecal samples were collected from diarrheic calves (n=51)

at different private farms and diarrheic children cases (n-56) from different clinical laboratories and hospitals in Ismailia governorate, Egypt. All Samples were collected separately in sterile plastic bags, labeled with history, age and date of collection, ice packed and transferred to the laboratory within minimum time of delay.

2- Isolation and identification of *E.coli*:

Samples collected were enriched firstly on trypticase soya broth then a loopful from each sample was inoculated separately onto MacConkey's agar and incubated at 37°C for 24 hours for primary isolation. Separate lactose fermenting colony was picked up to be cultured on Sorbitol MacConkey's agar and incubated at 37°C and 42°C for 24 hours, on sheep blood agar and on EMB media and incubated at 37°C for 24h. Bacterial colonies were identified morphologically using Gram's stain as well as biochemically using methods described by (Qunin et al., 2002)

3-Serotyping:

The somatic (O) antigen was determined by slide agglutination test according to (Edwards and Ewing, 1972), while Flagellar (H) antigen serotyping was carried out using tube method according to (Davies and Wray, 1997).

4- Genetic detection of different virulence factors genes of *E.coli* isolates by using polymerase chain reaction:

A-Extraction of DNA from *E.coli* isolates by boiling method according Usein et al. (2009).

B-Polymerase chain reaction: DNA samples were tested [in 50 µl. Reaction volume in a 0.2 ml PCR tube , containing PCR buffer] (50 mM KCl

, 10 mM tris - Hcl , 1mM Mgcl₂) each dNTPS (Deoxy nucleotide Triphosphate) 200 uM each (dATP , dGTP , dCTP and dTTP) , [Two primer pairs each at 50 picomol / reaction] and 0.5 of taq DNA polymerase . Thermal cycling in a programmable heating block (Coy corporation, Grasslake, Michan, USA) was done.

c-Screening of PCR products: ten µl of amplified PCR product was analyzed by electrophoresis on a 2% agarose gel stained with 0.5 µg of ethidium bromide / ml. Electrophoresis was carried out in 1X TAE buffer at 80 volt for 1 hour. Gels were visualized under UV transilluminator (UVP, UK) and photographed.

5-Gene sequencing of ESAT 1 gene in isolated *E.coli*:

PCR products were purified using MSB Spin PCRapace kit (**Invitex GmbH, Germany**) according to the instructions of the manufacturer. Sequencing was performed using Big Dye Terminator v3.1, and 1µl purified PCR product were added to 1µl Big Dye terminator. One µl of 5 -fold-concentrated buffer and 1.3µl single primer then completed to 19µl nuclease free water (**promega**) and subjected to amplification in thermal cycler (**Applied Biosystems**) under the following conditions, 96°C (30 sec.), 96°C (10 sec.), 50°C (5 sec.), 60°C (4 min.).The labeled products were then analyzed by an ABI Prism 3100 Genetic Analyzer (**Applied Biosystems, USA**).

Sequences were edited and assembled using SeqMan Pro software included in DNASTAR Lasergene package (**Bioinformatics pioneer DNASTAR, Inc., Wisconsin, USA**).

Table (1): list of primers used for PCR assay

Gene	Primer	Oligonucleotide Sequence (5-3)	Ref	
STX1	KS7	CCCGGATCCATGAAAAAACATTATTAATAGC	Zweifel et al., 2006	
	KS8	CCCGAATTCAGCTATTCTGAGTCAACG		
STX2	VT2e	AATACATTATGGGAAAGTAATA		
	VT2f	TAAACTGCACTTCAGCAAAT		
eaeA	SK1	CCCGAATTCGGCACAAGCATAAGC		
	SK2	CCCGGATCCGTCTCGCCAGTATTCG		
ehxA	HlyA1	GGTGCAGCAGAAAAAGTTGTAG		
	HlyA4	TCTCGCCTGATAGTGTGTTGGTA		
Lt	elt1	ATTTACGGCGTTACTATCCTC		Vu-Khac et al., 2007
	elt2	TTTTGGTCTCGGTCAGATATG		
Sta	Sta5	ATTTTCTTCTGTATTGTCTT	Al-Gallas et al, 2007	
	Sta3	CACCCGGTACAAGCAGGATT		
aggR	aggR-F	CTAATTGTACAATCGATGTA	Sabrina et al., 2007	
	aggR-R	AGAGTCCATCTCTTTGATAAG		
bfpA	EP1	AATGGTGCTTGCGCTTGCTGC	Mercado et al.,2004	
	EP2	GCCGCTTTATCCAACCTGGTA		
F4 (K88)	F4-F	GCTGCATCTGCTGCATCTGGTATG	Vu-Khac et al.,2007	
	F4-R	CCACTGAGTGCTGGTAGTTACAGCC		
F5 (K99)	F5-F	TGCGACTACCAATGCTTCTG		
	F5-R	TATCCACCATTAGACGGAGC		
astA	astA-1	CCATCAACACAGTATATC	Osek, 2002	
	astA-2	GGTCGCGAGTGACGGCTTTGT		

Results

Table (2): The prevalence of suspected *E. coli* isolates from diarrheic cases

Origin	Total Number of the collected samples	Number of isolated <i>E.coli</i>	Percentage
Calves	51	32	62.7%
Human	56	44	78.5%
Total	106	76	71,69%

Table (3): Correlation between EAST1 gene and other virulence factors genes in different *E. coli* serogroups isolated from calves and human:

Serotype and number	Stx 1	Stx 2	EaeA	ehxA	L T	S T	agg R	bf p	F4	F5	EAS T1
O157:H7(7).EHEC	+	+	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	2/7
O26:H11(6). EHEC	+	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	1/6
O126:H27(7).EAEC	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	6/7
OUT*:H16(4).EAEC	-	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	4/4
O6:H16(9).ETEC	-	-	-	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	9/9
O6:HNM**(7).ETEC	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	6/7
O86a:H10(4).EPEC	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	2/4
O115:HUT*** (3) calf.EP	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	+	-	+	1/3
O8:H4 Calf (9).ETEC	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	2/9
O8:H21 Calf (9).ETEC	-	-	-	-	-	+	-	-	-	+	1/9
O114:HUT Calf. (4).Ayp EPEC	-	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	0/4
O48:HNM Calf (7).EHEC	+	+	-	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	0/7

* Somatic antigen untypable; ** Non Motile strain; *** Flagellar antigen untypable

Fig. (1): illustrate phylogenetic analysis of EAST1gene positive *E.coli* strains from human and calf origin.

Discussion

In the present study, the prevalence of the EAST1 gene and its relationship with serotype and other virulence genes in *E. coli* isolated from calves and human diarrhea was examined.

As shown in Table (3) , it was clearly demonstrated that EAST1 gene was found in most human strains accompanied with LT and ST gene in Enterotoxigenic strains (O6:H16), aggR (Fimbrial antigen-specific gene) in Enteroaggregative strains (O126:H27) and with shiga toxins and intimin genes in Enterohemorrhagic strains (O157:H7 and O26:H11) . The EAST1 gene was also detected accompanied with other virulence factors genes from patients with

diarrhea in human strains isolated by (Yamamoto and Echeverria, 1996).

ETEC strains are generally considered to represent a pathogenic prototype: the organisms colonize the surface of the small bowel mucosa and elaborate their enterotoxins, giving rise to a net secretory state. ETEC strains cause diarrhea through the action of the enterotoxins LT and ST. These strains may express an LT only, an ST only, or both an LT and an ST. These toxins have recently been reviewed by (Sears and Kaper, 1996). The major virulence factor, and a defining characteristic of EHEC (as O157: H7), is Stx (shiga like toxin). This potent cytotoxin is the factor that leads to death and many other symptoms in patients infected with EHEC (O'Brien

et al., 1983). EAEC adherence to the intestinal mucosa requires AAF and adherence factors. Three AAF structural subunits encoded by *aggA* (AAF/I), *aafA* (AAF/II) and *agg-3* (AAF/III) on the 60–65 MDa pAA plasmids have been described. Both *aggA* and *aafA* are regulated by the transcriptional activator AggR. **(Bernier et al., 2002).**

In the present study, only 4 bovine strains (3 Enterotoxigenic strains " O8:H4 / O8:H21 " and 1 enteropathogenic strain " O115: HUT ") with adherence factor F5 (K99) were also positive for the EAST1 gene. The high prevalence of EAST1 among *E. coli* with adherence factor was also demonstrated among bovine strains isolated by **(Bertin et al., 1998).** The most common observed fimbriae on ETEC from calves with diarrhea are F5, also named K99 and F41 **(Contrepolis et al. 1989).** K99 antigen is a fimbrial adhesin distinct from the capsular polysaccharide K antigens **(Orskov et al. 1975).** Two biological classes of enterotoxins are produced by ETEC: heat labile (LT) and heat stable (STa and STb) **(Scotland et al. 1985).** Most bovine ETEC produce STa enterotoxin and K99 fimbriae **(Kaeckenbeeck, 1981).**

The nucleotide sequences from the EAST1 gene were highly conserved among *E. coli* strains. Since the EAST1 gene is widely distributed among different categories of diarrhea-associated *E. coli*, EAaggEC **(Savarino et al. 1993)**, ETEC **(Yamamoto and Echeverria, 1996)**, and diffusely adhering *E. coli* (strains 73-1 and 5-2 **(Yamamoto et al, 1993)**), EAST1 gene may be on a transposon **(Yamamoto and Echeverria, 1996).**

The phylogenetic analysis of EAST1 sequence reveals that the sequence of east1 demonstrated in four lineages, lineage I represent the major one and encompass a group of phylogenetically

closely related strains, being from human or calf origin. It divided into two distinct sublineages A and B. Sublineage A includes strains from human origin and (3) *E. coli* strains from calf. Sublineage B includes the remaining strain of calf origin with human strains. Lineage II and III cover strains from human origin. Lineage IV represented by EAST1 sequence on reference plasmid, which distinctly separated from the last three lineages indicating, the presence of EAST1 gene in the present study strains on the chromosome not on plasmid.

Briefly, the results of the present study indicate that the EAST1 gene is widely distributed among different *E. coli* pathotypes isolated from calves and human with diarrhea. Therefore, EAST1 toxin gene may represent an additional virulence determinant playing a role in the pathogenesis of *E. coli* diarrhea in both human and animal. Moreover, the presence of the EAST1 gene makes the bovine *E. coli* strains similar to human EAST1-positive isolates that are potentially able to induce diarrhea.

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